

Identification of Career Needs and Dual Career Development among Students in Secondary Schools in Sebei Sub-Region

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Abstract: Dual careers have become a relevant matter in the world of work as one of the tools that can improve social life. In that regard, this study sought to examine the influence of identification of career needs on dual career development among students. The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative approaches in which a population of 360 people involving headteachers, deputy headteachers, Directors of Studies, Career guidance teachers, Games teachers; Sports officers; and students who have been involved in games and sports in the schools were targeted. The study used a sample of 186 people selected using purposive, simple random and cluster sampling techniques. Data was collected using a validated and pre-tested self-administered questionnaire and interview guide. Analysis of the quantitative data collected was done using descriptive and inferential statistics generated by the SPSS; while analysis of the qualitative data was done using thematic and content analysis.

The findings of the study revealed that for identification of career needs and dual career development, $R^2 = .297$, $F=77.304$, $Sig= .000 < .05$ for academic career while for sports career $R^2 = .072$, $F=14.184$, $Sig= .000 < .05$. The study concluded that identification of students' career needs had a higher magnitude of influence for academic than for sports career development. The study finally recommends that to be able to support students in identification of career needs, the teachers should be trained and empowered with the requisite information about the various careers available for students to choose from.

Keywords: Identification of Career Needs, Dual Career Development, Students, Sebei Sub-Region.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background

The goal of dual career development, as consistently stated in policy statements, is to help students develop the knowledge, abilities, and attitudes necessary to comprehend and succeed both inside and outside of the classroom, supporting both personal and societal economic performance (OECD, 2010). In a nutshell, dual career development is a plan designed to help someone get ready for a variety of professional choices following graduation. Considering numerous employment choices beyond your time in school is a wise decision in the present climate, regardless of your objectives, and it's crucial to start early. A variety of cooperative and partnership activities are essential to the success of professions education programs in schools and colleges. The growth of academic and athletic careers among secondary school pupils was the main focus of this study.

In the majority of the nations where dual career arrangements have been established for some time, there are occasionally gaps in the strong agreements between the sport system and the educational or professional worlds. They might also be lacking in a stable legal system or political strategy. The development and improvement of sustainable dual career programs that allow for individualized arrangements for exceptional and elite athletes worldwide, whether in their capacity as student-athletes or employee-athletes, could benefit from careers education.

State of Careers Education in Uganda

Dual careers are still quite new, even though career education has long been practiced in Uganda. However, it has been noted that Ugandans continue to change careers. It is wise to give studies on dual careers and career education considerable thought. The Ministry of Education and Sports (MoES) in Uganda has as its vision “*Quality Education and Sports for All,*” and its mission “*To provide for, support, guide, coordinate, regulate, and promote delivery of quality Education and Sports to all persons in Uganda; for national integration, individual, and national development*” (ESSP, 2017). This suggests that Uganda's MoES takes into account the dual career development of all learners, specifically academic and athletic. The ESSP FY 2017/18 - 2019/20 has only designated 32 schools as sports centers, nevertheless. As a result, career education is not typically prioritized in schools for the benefit of students. Therefore, it is still unclear how the learners' development of dual careers was affected by the lack of emphasis placed on careers education.

Careers Education within the Curriculum

As was already said, the MoES in Uganda is a dual ministry since, in line with its mission, it aims to help students advance both their academic and athletic abilities. In an ideal world, the educational system would prepare students for careers in both athletics and academia. There is no official training for service providers in Uganda's educational curriculum, despite the fact that career education services were created in the USA more than 100 years ago. The educational programs in Uganda are structured to get students ready for the next level of learning.

Prior to 2020, Uganda's secondary education curriculum gave priority to topic knowledge at the expense of helping students develop marketable and transferrable skills and competences (NCDC, 2020). The previous secondary education curriculum was initially created for a select group of exceptional kids headed for careers in the public sector. As a result, every learner will be able to acquire understandings and skills in accordance with his or her capacity, according to NCDC (2020). NCDC further affirms that the new curriculum will be designed so that it gives every learner the chance to gain the knowledge, skills, and attitudes they need as well as the opportunity to receive the proper acknowledgment for their accomplishments while they are in school (NCDC, 2020).

Career instructors have been in charge of career education in secondary schools in Uganda up until the introduction of the new lower secondary school curriculum. These educators work to provide knowledge on the following topics and frequently take part in activities that are linked to them, including assessing career needs, creating career chances, fusing student needs with professional opportunities, and routine monitoring (NCDC, 2017). Their level of interaction with the kids differs from one school to the next due to a variety of circumstances, including time constraints, facilitation, and support from other stakeholders, to name a few. The teachers work hard to help the students establish personal development plans that should be founded on their beliefs, aspirations, and self-awareness.

Statement of the Problem

Despite provision of career education to support students' identification of career needs in secondary schools, dual career development remains a significant obstacle. Due to its mission of offering top-notch sports and education to all students, Uganda's Ministry of Education and Sports supports the conventional dual career growth. In order to help learners transition from one career to another in the 21st century successfully and without major obstacles, dual career development is the way to go. Secondary schools support students in identification of career needs through their careers teachers in this regard. However, a lot of Sebei students have had trouble preparing for both a career in academics and a career in sports. Numerous students are still struggling with the issue of dual career development, and the majority of them are unable to conduct efficient self-evaluations, explore opportunities, identify career opportunities, integrate their goals with employee needs, or conduct routine choice monitoring (OECD, 2018). There are research on sports and athletics (Taras, 2005; Yiannakis and Melnick, 2001), but there is little information on how career education affects the growth of dual careers in Uganda, particularly in the Sebei sub-region. Before students enter the final stages of their education, secondary schools should ensure that there is a balanced progression of their careers. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of support in identification of career needs towards dual career development among students in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region.

Purpose

To establish the influence of support in identification of career needs on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Significance of Study

The results of this study may help stakeholders in different ways; for instance:

It will assist the Ministry of Education and Sports in making sure that Uganda has the chance to create an advanced secondary level curriculum, which will be essential in shaping young people into become more independent, proactive professionals capable of competing for jobs right out of school, especially if they cannot afford to pursue a more rigorous study at the university level.

It will assist the District Education Officers in promoting the National Curriculum Development Centre's (NCDC) curriculum in order to encourage dual career development among Ugandan youth. For better outcomes in both academics and athletics, it will allow school officials to give their kids' dual career development first priority. The findings might serve as a foundation for the academia.

Scope of the Study

The study was done in secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region of eastern Uganda, close to the Kenya-Uganda border. The region is located 295 kilometers (183 miles) northeast of Kampala, the capital city of Uganda, along 01 24N, 34 27E. Although it is a mountainous area with challenging terrain, it is well known for producing some of the best athletes in the nation. The Sebei sub-region was chosen for this study because it has recently produced the top athletes, both men and women, and because many students there are experimenting with dual career development, particularly in athletics. The focused on influence of identifying career needs on dual career development among secondary school students in the Sebei sub-region. This was due to the USPA (2019) report's indication that dual career development in secondary schools was weak. The period from 2015 to 2021 was considered for the study because this was the period that witnessed renewed efforts in career education with challenges in dual career development (Otwine and Oonyu, 2018).

Conceptual Framework

Source: Cosh and Tully (2014); and Rugangila (2019).

Fig. 1.1 Conceptual Framework

Theoretical Review

The study adopted two theories: Bandura's Theory and Super's Self-Concept Theory.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

Albert Bandura proposed the Social Cognitive Theory in 1986 as an expansion of the prior Social Learning Theory he had created in 1977. According to the idea, learning can be partially attributed to observing others while taking into account social interactions, personal experiences, and outside media influences. According to the hypothesis, when individuals

watch a model engage in an action and experience the results, they retain the chronology of events and make use of it to direct future behavior. The Social Cognitive Theory is put out from an agent perspective, which contends that people are self-developing, self-regulating, self-reflective, and proactive rather than just being formed by their environments or inner forces (Pajares, 2009). According to Pajares (2009), human agency primarily takes three forms: individual, proxy, and collective. Individual agency refers to a person's direct influence on the environment, while proxy agency refers to another person's efforts to protect the individual's interests.

The central idea of social cognitive theory, according to Bandura (1988), is that information is acquired or learned by observation of models. The models may come from media sources or interpersonal imitation. Effective modeling offers overarching principles and methods for handling various circumstances. According to the idea, learning is most likely to happen when the observer and the model have a high degree of identification and the observer also has a high level of self-efficacy (Urich, 2017). Self-efficacy is the degree to which a person has confidence in their ability to learn a specific skill. Self-efficacy beliefs influence behavior through intervening motivational, cognitive, and affective processes, making them a significant set of proximal determinants of human motivation, affect, and action (Bandura, 1989).

Bandura defined self-efficacy as the confidence in one's ability to plan and carry out the actions necessary to handle potential scenarios (Bandura, 1988). Bandura and other academics have discovered that a person's level of self-efficacy significantly affects how they handle objectives, duties, and difficulties. High self-efficacy people are more inclined to think they can solve complex challenges and bounce back fast from failures and disappointments. Low self-efficacy makes people less self-assured and less secure in their abilities, which makes them shy away from difficult jobs. Therefore, behavior performance is heavily influenced by self-efficacy. High levels of self-efficacy increase the likelihood that observers will engage in observational learning practices (Bandura, 1989).

Mastery experience, a process that aids a person in completing straightforward tasks that pave the way for more difficult goals, can be used to build or develop self-efficacy; Improving physical and emotional states means making sure a person is rested and at ease before attempting a new task. Social modeling offers a recognizable model that illustrates the processes that accomplish a behavior. Less patient and less unhurried people are more likely to fail to engage in desired conduct. Verbal persuasion is motivating someone to finish a job or adopt a particular behavior (McAlister et al., 2008).

Identification enables the spectator to experience a 1:1 likeness with the model, which may increase the likelihood that the observer will carry out the modeled behavior (Bandura, 1988). People are more likely to imitate the behaviour of someone they can relate to. The likelihood that the observer learns and imitates the modeled behavior increases with the number of similarities or emotional connections that are seen between them. SCT is frequently used in media studies as it relates to sports, health, education, and other topics. For instance, Hardin and Greer in 2009 researched the gender-typing of sports within the theoretical framework of social cognitive theory and proposed that gender perception of sports among American college students was highly influenced by gender-role socialization and sports media use. Therefore, Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory was appropriate in predicting the results of this study on career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory

The notion of career development examines ways to enhance professional development, career trajectories, and overall job satisfaction. Understanding professional development theory can be a crucial first step in figuring out your fundamental values, aptitudes, and chosen route. While different career development theories make different claims, all of them stress the value of forming meaningful professional ambitions and cultivating a positive emotional relationship with one's work. The developmental hypothesis was developed by Donald Super on the premise that your self-perception evolves. The way a person values their profession and the goals they set is shaped by time and experience. According to this view, a person's lifetime constitutes their entire "career." Five stages of career growth were identified by Super: Growth, Exploration, Establishment, Maintenance and Decline.

Super believed that how satisfied people were with their careers depended on how they perceived themselves at each of these five stages of development. A work-life balance, for example, may be more important at the maintenance stage than in the establishment stage. Even if a person's career doesn't change, experience and time might change how they perceive their area of work. This study on career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region was successfully supported by Super's Developmental Self-Concept Theory, it was found.

2. EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies conducted in developed nations have looked into the difficulties students face when trying to identify their career needs. For instance, it has been noted that there are a variety of obstacles to achieving sustainable individual and sports-based development in high performance sport (i.e., the integration of sport with education/work) policy recommendations for the European Union (EU) nations in 2012 (EU Guidelines, 2012). Research on athletes' dual careers and policy development in the member states were stimulated by the following distribution of money for sports projects across Europe. Stambulova and Wylleman (2019) discovered a variety of advantages of multiple careers in their assessment of dual career research, including student development on an individual level, improved athletic performance, and improved life satisfaction over the long run.

In addition, studies looking into the career paths of elite athletes have shown that these individuals typically take one of three paths: (a) concentrating solely on sport; (b) combining sport and education/work while prioritizing sports-based development; or (c) building a stable dual career pathway. Only the stable dual career trajectory has been found to protect athletes' overall personal development, employability, and re-integration into society after careers in elite sport (Barriopedro et al., 2019; L'opez de Subijana et al., 2020). These three pathways, referred to as linear, convergent, and parallel (Torregrosa et al., 2015), are associated with different psycho-social implications of career transitions.

On the other hand, although research clarifying the psycho-social outcomes of athletes' career behaviour exists, fairly little is known about the developmental curves of a dual career that would explain how the career pathways found among elite athletes are formed and the role they play in dual career (dis)continuation. As late adolescence has been identified as a transitional period in which athletes progressing to senior sport are challenged to combine higher levels of competition with other roles in life (Stambulova et al., 2015), it is important to consider how the dual career developmental trajectory during this phase becomes embedded. Research with talented adolescents transitioning to elite sport has revealed that many experience role strain and exhaustion in their efforts to balance increasing, often contradictory, cultural expectations to excel (Elliott et al., 2018; Gledhill & Harwood, 2015; Knight et al., 2018).

Baron-Thiene and Alfermann (2015) reported that 29.6% of dual career adolescents in German elite sport schools dropped out of sport prior to reaching their peak performance. Furthermore, an emerging body of research has identified underlying gender structures that influence athletes' experiences and decisions about their dual careers. For example, although female athletes' motivation for their sport is similar to males, they are more likely to invest into educational and dual career goals and identities (Ekengren et al., 2018; Moazami-Goodarzi et al., 2020) as well as to story their lives along multiple cultural narratives (Ekengren et al., 2020). Studies that investigated athletes' dual careers within handball (Ekengren et al., 2018), basketball (Tekavc et al., 2015), and football (Harrison et al., 2020) reported that, unlike their male peers, the majority of elite level female players pursued or were planning to pursue a dual career at the level of higher education, providing further support to the assertion that engendering the life careers of athletes is salient from adolescence to adulthood (Ryba et al., 2015).

Furthermore, Baron-Thiene and Alfermann (2015) and Ronkainen, Watkins, and Ryba (2016) reported female athletes having more physical complaints and exhaustion than their male counterparts, with many women receiving little emotional support from their coaches and parents and feeling lonely. These types of experiences partly contributed to the decision by female athletes to withdraw from sport and focus on education, work, and family. Based on the ethnographic study in the specialized classes at Denmark's elite sport schools, Skrubbeltrang et al (2018) argued that even when there is the intention to support equal opportunities for adolescent athletes to develop a dual career, gender expectations and sport shape an adolescent athlete's future perspective on what career is (im)possible. Feminists scholars have asserted that this so-called 'gender gap' across the (sub)fields of sport and education is sustained by hierarchical gendered logic of patriarchal societies, whereby identity is inevitably linked to (often binary) meanings of femininity and masculinity (Kavoura et al., 2015).

The social and psychological implications of the pervasively gendered life-world for an individual is that presumably neutral identity positions, such as athlete, teacher or coach, are implicitly woven into particular ways of thinking, feeling, and behaving. This, in turn, makes the individual either vulnerable or rewarded, contingent on their transgression or compliance with gender ideologies at a given (sub)cultural and historical conjuncture. As the dual career discourse has been mobilized at the intersection of sport and education, each with distinct stereotypical views of high- and low-

achieving gendered identities, it is pertinent to carefully scrutinize the assumed normalcy that, compared to their male peers, female athletes aspire more towards educational and dual career goals (Ryba, 2018).

3. METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with both qualitative and quantitative paradigms was used. Kothari (2006) affirms that the main idea behind using this type of design is to better define an opinion, attitude, or behaviour held by a group of people on a given subject. This is exactly what this study set out to establish about career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools. The primary data were collected through the self-administered questionnaires and face-to-face interviews. On the other hand, the secondary data were obtained through reading literature and documents on career education and dual career development. Secondary data are useful for researcher to detect variations of situations over time so as to support primary data (Amin, 2005).

The target population for the study consisted of various categories of people who included members of the headteachers (15) and deputy headteachers (15) of the selected secondary schools, Directors of Studies (15, DOS), career guidance teachers (15), games teachers (30), sports officers (03), students who have been involved in games and sports (267) in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. The total target population of study constituted of 360 people. Basing on the Glenn (1992) sampling table, the sample of the study constituted of 186 respondents who were sampled using purposive and cluster sampling techniques. Table 1.1 presents the summary of the population, sample size and sampling techniques used in the study.

Table 1.1: Population, Sample Size and Sampling Techniques used in the Study

Category	Population	Sample Size	Sampling Technique
Sports Officers	03	03	Census
Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Deputy Headteachers	15	08	Purposive
Directors of Studies	15	08	Purposive
Teachers (CG, Games/Sports)	45	23	Cluster Sampling
Students	267	136	Cluster Sampling
Total	360	186	

Source: District Education Registries for Kapchorwa, Kween and Bukwo (2021)

The study used two methods of data collection, the questionnaire (survey) method and the interview method. The questionnaire method was used because it has several advantages over some other methods in that it is cheap, easy to use, contains standardized items often with determined responses and easy to analyze the data collected. In this study, the Self-Administered Questionnaire (SAQ) tool was used to collect data from the teachers and students. This is because according to Johnson and Onwuegbuzie (2004), SAQs are ideal for studies involving large sample sizes and large geographic areas. Since the teachers and students were many in number and from a large geographical area, the questionnaire method was appropriate.

The interview method was used to collect data from the Sports Officers, headteachers, deputy headteachers and the career-guidance teachers because according to Kothari (2006), face-to-face interview method has the ability to gather in-depth detail from the interviewee. Interviewing participants can paint a picture of what happened in a specific event, tell us their perspective of such event, as well as give other social cues. Also, according to Oso and Onen, (2008), the interview guide as a tool is ideal because it permits the researcher to seek clarification and the interviewee can also ask for clarification thereby provide information that cannot be directly observed as well as obtain historical information about a phenomenon under investigation.

To ensure quality control, the instruments of data collection were tested for validity and reliability. The research instrument was validated through consultation with supervisors and a value of CVI of 0.81 was obtained implying good validity. On the other hand, the reliability of the instrument was assessed by first piloting the instrument with a few respondents who were not part of the final sample and using the split-half technique, the Chronbach reliability coefficient of 0.894 was obtained which according to George and Mallery (2003) scale, was interpreted as good reliability.

The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to compute descriptive statistics i.e. frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. From the descriptive statistic (means) the inferential statistics i.e. simple

linear regression that formed the basis of the conclusion was generated. For qualitative data analysis, collected data were transcribed, coded, categorized and themes built through content analysis. This was meant to enhance readability and understanding of the research findings by a larger public interested in issues of career education and dual career development among students in secondary schools in Uganda.

4. STUDY FINDINGS

Demographic Data of Respondents

The respondents were required to indicate their sex, age bracket, level of education and marital status. The detailed results about each characteristic are presented in Table 1.2.

Table 1.2: Demographic Data of Respondents

Category	Frequency (f)	Percent (%)
Gender		
Male	122	65.9
Female	63	34.1
Total	185	100.0
Age Bracket		
20-29 Years	126	68.1
30-39 Years	23	12.4
40-49 Years	24	13.0
Above 50 Years	12	6.5
Total	185	100.0
Education Level		
Diploma	20	10.8
Degree	30	16.2
Masters	12	6.5
A-level	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0
Responsibility		
Deputy Headteachers	12	6.5
Headteachers	8	4.3
Teachers	42	22.7
Students	123	66.5
Total	185	100.0

Source: Primary data (2022)

Out of the 185 respondents who completed the self-administered questionnaires, there were more male than female respondents. According to Table 4.2, 65.9% of the respondents were male while 34.1% of them were female respondents. This implies that in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, more men than women have been deployed to teach the students. From Table 1.2, majority (68.1%) of the respondents were in the age bracket of 20-29 years old while 12.4% were in the age bracket of 30-39 years old. Another 13.0% of them were in the age bracket of 40-49 years while only 6.5% were above 50 years of age. This implied that majority of the respondents were young adults who are often have vibrant interest in career development for their future lives.

The findings also showed that majority (66.5%) of the respondents were of A-level students which was the focus of the study. A-level students were considered because they at a critical stage of career determination as they prepare to tertiary education. Data in Table 1.2 further indicated that 16.2% of the respondents had degrees and 10.8% had diplomas. These were mainly the teachers of games and sports who were also considered vital in provision of data for this study. At least 6.5% of the respondents had masters degrees. These too were teachers that participated in the study. This implies that all the respondents who participated in this study had an appropriate level of education to have a clear understanding of the items in the self-administered questionnaire. Thus, it is presumed that the data they provided can be reliable in making precise conclusions about the study.

Data presented in Table 1.2 also revealed that 66.5% of the respondents were students who formed the biggest proportion of the unit of analysis. Another 22.7% were classroom teachers who also doubled as games/sports teachers and were

therefore, another important category in the unit of analysis. At least 6.5% and 4.3% were the deputy headteachers and headteachers respectively. The proportions of the respondents by designation reflects the representativeness of the respondents in the population of study and therefore, the results of the study may be generalized to the entire target population of study in Sebei sub-region.

Identification of Career Needs and Dual Career Development

The study investigated the influence of identification of career needs on dual career development among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. In order to attain an appropriate conclusion about this study, it was prudent to first consider analysis of the descriptive statistics for both identification of career needs and for dual career development. Then from the descriptive analysis, the we generated inferential statistics by running linear regression analysis using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS ver. 20). We selected 15 secondary schools with at least five schools from each of the three districts that constitute Sebei sub-region. These are Bukwo, Kapchorwa and Kween districts. This was done to ensure representativeness so as to generalize the findings of this study to the entire Sebei sub-region. Data in Table 1.3 represents the descriptive statistics for identification of career needs by the students in the secondary schools under study.

Table 1.3: Descriptive Statistics for Identification of Career Needs by Students

Items on Identification of Career Needs	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
In this school, we carry out psychological testing to understand the interests of the students before helping them to identify career needs	15.1	14.6	56.8	13.5	2.69	.890
We also try to find out what the students value in order to help them identify career needs	0.0	5.9	49.2	44.9	3.39	.599
We endeavour to assess the students' abilities in order to help them identify career needs	1.6	11.4	40.0	47.0	3.32	.739
We consider it necessary to find out the kind of skills the students have before supporting them to identify career needs	1.6	3.2	47.0	48.1	3.42	.638
We also consider personal circumstances in order to support the students in identifying career needs	1.6	30.8	43.2	24.3	2.90	.781
We carry out simulation exercises in order to help students identify career needs	2.2	27.6	28.6	41.6	3.10	.879
We endeavour to carry out in-depth interviews with the students before supporting them to identify career needs	2.7	62.2	23.2	11.9	2.44	.736
Overall Mean					3.07	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Students are rarely supported; 1.1 - 2.0 = Students are fairly supported;

2.1 - 3.0 = Students are moderately supported; 3.1 - 4.0 = students are well supported

From the data in Table 1.3, it was revealed that majority (56.8%) of the respondents acknowledged that psychological testing was carried out to understand the interests of the students before helping them to identify career needs. Another 13.5% of them strongly agreed while 14.6% disagreed and 15.1% of them strongly disagreed that psychological testing was carried out to understand the interests of the students before helping them to identify career needs. This implies that in some schools, psychological testing was carried out but in some schools, it was not done. The data in Table 1.3 further showed that 49.2% of the respondents agreed and 44.9% strongly agreed that career teachers tried to find out what the students valued in order to help them identify career needs. Only a small proportion of 5.9% disagreed career teachers tried to find out what the students valued in order to help them identify career needs.

The findings in Table 1.3 also revealed that 47.0% and 40.0% strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the career teachers endeavoured to assess the students' abilities in order to help them identify career needs. However, 11.4% and 1.6% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the career teachers endeavoured to assess the students' abilities in order to help them identify career needs. This also implied that some career teachers make an effort to assess the students' abilities prior to offering any help to students to identify their career needs.

Furthermore, the findings indicated that 48.1% strongly agreed with another 47.0% agreeing that career teachers considered it necessary to find out the kind of skills the students had before supporting them to identify career needs. However, 3.2% disagreed and 1.6% strongly disagreed that career teachers ever considered it necessary to find out the kind of skills the students had before supporting them to identify career needs. Similarly, 43.2% of the respondents agreed and 24.3% strongly agreed that career teachers also considered personal circumstances in order to support the students in identifying career needs. At least 30.8% disagreed and 1.6% strongly disagreed that career teachers also considered personal circumstances in order to support the students in identifying career needs. This implies that in some cases the career teachers considered personal interests and circumstances before attempting to support the students in identification of their career needs.

The findings in Table 1.3 also revealed that 41.6% of the respondents strongly agreed and another 28.6% of them agreed that career teachers carried out simulation exercises in order to help students identify career needs. Some 27.6% disagreed and 2.2% strongly disagreed in this regard. However, majority (62.2%) disagreed with 2.7% strongly disagreeing that career teachers endeavoured to carry out in-depth interviews with the students before supporting them to identify career needs. Only a marginal 23.2% agreed and 11.9% strongly agreeing that career teachers ever endeavoured to carry out in-depth interviews with the students before supporting them to identify career needs. The overall mean for all the items on identification of career needs was 3.07, which according to the legend at the bottom of Table 1.3 implies that students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region are moderately supported in identification of their career needs.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Academic Careers

Table 1.4 presents descriptive statistics on development of academic careers.

Table 1.4: Development of Academic Careers

Items on Development of Academic Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
Most of the students who have passed through this school have ended up as school teachers	15.7	18.9	24.9	40.5	2.90	1.104
The school has produced several medical doctors since its inception	25.9	7.6	41.1	25.4	2.66	1.122
Most of the students aspire to become lawyers	13.0	25.4	49.7	11.9	2.61	.860
Majority of the students in this school would want to be social workers to serve their communities	1.1	33.0	36.8	29.2	2.94	.815
The school has produced a number of people now working as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers	25.4	50.3	9.7	14.6	2.14	.960
The students in this school aspire to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime	0.0	16.8	63.8	19.5	3.03	.603
Students would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics	2.2	35.1	49.7	13.0	2.74	.707
Overall Mean					2.72	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Academic careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Academic careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Academic careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Academic careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.4 revealed that 24.9% and 40.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as school teachers. However, 18.9% and 15.7% disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that most of the students who had passed through the secondary schools had ended up as school teachers. This implied that not all the students who had studied in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had become teachers. The findings further revealed that 41.1% and 25.4% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. However, 25.9% and 7.6% of the respondents strongly disagreed and disagreed respectively that the schools had produced several medical doctors since their inception. This too, implied that the schools had not produced several medical doctors, perhaps some few but not several.

Furthermore, the findings showed that 49.7% and 11.9% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that most of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region aspired to become lawyers. Similarly, 36.8% and 29.2% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that majority of the students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would want to be social workers to serve their communities. However, 50.3% and 25.4% of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively that the secondary schools had produced a number of people now working in the public sector as Public Administrators such as Chief Administrative Officers. This implied that perhaps on few of the students from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had ended up as Public Administrators.

The findings also showed that majority (63.8%) and 19.5% of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the students in the secondary schools aspired to become Engineers of different categories in their future lifetime. Similarly, majority (49.7% and 13.0% agreed and strongly agreed respectively that students studying in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region would like to end up as Statisticians working with different organizations dealing with statistics. The overall mean for all the items on development of academic careers was 2.72 which according to the legend at the bottom of Table 1.4 implies that development of academic careers has been moderately prioritized by students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region for their future life.

Before, considering the influence of identification of career needs on development of academic careers among the students, it was prudent to ascertain their relatedness. Therefore, the results in Table 1.5 show the relatedness of the identification of career needs to development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.5: Relatedness of Identification of Career Needs to Development of Academic Careers among Students in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	-.462	.389		-1.188	.236
Identifying career needs	1.006	.114	.545	8.792	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Academic Career Development

The results in Table 1.5 indicated a significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that identification of career needs was significantly related to development of academic careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. To determine the influence of identification of career needs on the development of academic careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, a linear regression was run using the transformed overall means in Table 1.3 (i.e. 3.07) for identification of career needs and that in Table 1.4 (i.e. 2.72) for development of academic careers. The results of the linear regression are presented in Table 1.6 and Table 1.7.

Table 1.6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.545 ^a	.297	.293	.928

a. Predictors: (Constant), Identifying career needs

From the results in Table 1.6, the R square value was .297 which can be converted to percent (.297 x 100) giving 29.7%. This means that for every unit effort in supporting students in identification of career needs in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, there was a 29.7% improvement in development of academic careers. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.7 were considered.

Table 1.7: Influence of Support in Identification of Career Needs on Development of Academic Careers among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	66.597	1	66.597	77.304	.000 ^b
	Residual	157.652	183	.861		
	Total	224.249	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Academic career Development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Identifying career needs

From Table 1.7 and at $r^2 = .297$ the sig = $.000 < .05$, implying that there is a strong significant influence of supporting students in identification of career needs and development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Table 1.8: Descriptive Statistics on Development of Sports Careers

Items on Development of Sports Careers	SD	D	A	SA	Mean	Std. Dev
There are students who would like to work as Sports Directors in future.	1.6	18.4	51.4	28.6	3.07	.730
Some of the students who completed from this school now work as Sports Managers	15.1	36.2	47.0	1.6	2.35	.752
A number of the students are now working as Directors in the sports field around the country	19.5	51.9	25.9	2.7	2.12	.742
Majority of our students are now Trainers in various sporting activities	2.2	25.9	69.7	2.2	2.72	.539
We have several of our former students who are Referees in the sports field	2.2	19.5	64.9	13.5	2.90	.639
Some of our students would want to work as Umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country	0.5	19.5	51.4	28.6	3.08	.706
Overall Mean					2.71	

Source: Primary data (2022)

Legend

0.0 - 1.0 = Sports careers not prioritized; 1.1 - 2.0 = Sports careers fairly prioritized;

2.1 - 3.0 = Sports careers moderately prioritized; 3.1-4.0 = Sports careers well prioritized

Data in Table 1.8 showed that majority (51.4%) of the respondents agreed and another 28.6% of them strongly agreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. However, a small proportion of 18.4% disagreed and 1.6% strongly disagreed that there were students who liked to work as sports directors in future. This implied that there were a significant number of students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region who had interest in development of a sports career. The results further showed that 47.0% of the respondents acknowledged that some of the students who completed from the secondary school in Sebei sub-region now work as sports managers. However, another 36.2% disagreed in this regard. This implies that while some of the students who completed from the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were already working as sports managers, the others were not. Perhaps they were engaged in other careers.

Furthermore, the results in Table 1.8 revealed that majority (51.9%) of the respondents disagreed with another 19.5% of them strongly disagreeing that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. At least 25.9% and 2.7% of them agreed and strongly agreed respectively that a number of the students were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. This implies that some few of the students who studied in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were now working as directors in the sports field around the country. The results also indicated that majority (69.7%) of the respondents acknowledged that most of the students were now trainers in various sporting activities. Similarly, majority (64.9%) of the respondents agreed and 13.5% of them strongly agreed that they had several of their former students who were referees in the sports field. Another 51.4% agreed and 28.6% strongly agreed that some of their students would want to work as umpires for some of the common sports activities in the country.

The overall mean for all the items on development of the sports careers was 2.71 which is according to the legend at the bottom of Table 1.8 implies that development of sports career among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region is moderately prioritized for their future life. Table 1.9 shows the relatedness of the identification of career needs to development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Table 1.9: Relatedness of Identification of career Needs to Development of Sports Careers among Students in Secondary Schools in Sebei sub-region

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.682	.274		6.141	.000
Identifying career needs	.327	.087	.268	3.766	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

The results in Table 1.9 indicated a significance value (Sig) of .000 implying that identification of career needs is also significantly related to development of sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Influence of Identification of Career Needs on Development of Sports Careers

To determine the influence of identification of career needs on the development of sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, a linear regression was run using the transformed overall means in Table 1.3 (i.e. 3.07) for identification of career needs and that in Table 1.8 (i.e. 2.71) for development of sports careers. The results of the linear regression are presented in Table 1.10 and Table 1.11.

Table 1.10: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.268 ^a	.072	.067	.860

a. Predictors: (Constant), Identifying career needs.

The R square value was .072 which can be converted to percent (.072 x 100) giving 7.2%. This means that for every unit change in supporting students in identification of career needs in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, development of sports careers improves by only 7.2%. To determine whether or not such a change causes a significant influence, the ANOVA results in Table 1.11 were considered.

Table 1.11: Influence of Support in Identification of Career Needs on Development of Sports Careers among Students in Sec. Schools in Sebei (ANOVA)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	10.489	1	10.489	14.184	.000 ^b
Residual	135.327	183	.739		
Total	145.816	184			

a. Dependent Variable: Sports career development

b. Predictors: (Constant), Identifying career needs

From Table 1.11 and at $r^2 = .072$ the $\text{sig} = .000 < .05$, implying that there is also a strong significant influence of identification of career needs on development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Qualitative Data

The quantitative results for development of both academic and sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were closely in agreement with the qualitative data gathered through face-to-face interviews with several participants. For instance, in a face-to-face interview with regard to description of the influence of identification of career needs on dual career development among students; one of the deputy headteachers (R-DHT-01) of the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, he said:

“Through identification teachers are able to identify the learner’s ability to participate in a given sporting activity. Monitoring and building more the capacity of the learners in the best area of career can change the behavior of the learners towards the academic and sports career. It enables the school administration to integrate the two careers (academic and sports). Through identification the said students can be linked to role models in the areas of their ability.”

From the above response, it is clear that the teachers engage learners in identification of career needs and try to encourage them to participate in specific sporting activities. In an interview with one director of studies (R-DOS-01), he said:

“Identification helps the learners to be specific in what they can do best in both academics and sports career. It enables the school administration to cater for the needs of the learners towards achieving best in academics and sports career: It helps the learner to go on with both academics and sports career.”

The response above further reveals that the teachers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region try to help students in identification of career needs. However, in another face-to-face interview with a headteacher (R-HT-01), he said:

“Identification is not a major issue of focus and is not being done in all schools since most sportsmen like athletes do not have interest. A case in point Athletes emulate their role models who have excelled in their field and consider academics a waste of time since sports is well paying. In that regard, career education is uncertain if a person can really make it or not.”

The implication from the headteacher’s response is that in some schools, teachers are not so much bothered about encouraging learners to participate in identification of career needs. However, the fact is that some of the students are just talented. For instance, in another interview with a director of studies (R-DOS-02), she said:

“Through career guidance identification of the needs and careers of our learners it’s a fact that most students in Sebei sub region are good in Athletics. These have been enabled through identifying the career needs of our learners. Identification of career needs enables learners to choose a path of their choice depending on the need identified. A case in point is learners who are good at Athletics as well as academics many choose the best he/she does among two.”

Given the director of studies response above, it implies that for those who are talented in both sports and academics, they have an option to choose one and concentrate on it. The danger is that instead of developing dual career, they end up developing one. This can be a disadvantage to them. In that regard, another director of studies (R-DOS-02) in another secondary schools in the Sebei sub-region said:

“Through career identification the less advantaged learners are now earn their living from their since career identification has enabled them to do so. Career identification and guidance has helped most learners to carry forward both their academics and sports. They are encouraged to build their academic careers alongside sports so as to progress concurrently especially in their communication skills.”

The response of the director of studies quoted above shows that when teachers help students in identification of career needs, it ultimately becomes useful to the less advantaged learners. This is because the students engage in both academic and sporting activities and in the event of failing to progress well in academics, they turn to the sporting careers which has helped many to earn a living. Another director of studies of a secondary school (R-DOS-03) was in agreement with his colleagues who had also been interviewed in the other schools. He said:

“Identification of career needs has got a positive influence some of our students through the identification at their career needs have also excelled in sport and academics. Some students had been weak in academic but through careers development and proper identification of their needs have excelled in sport. A case in point is Sigwa Abel who is seriously coming up in the field of athletics.”

From the responses of the participants in the quotations above, it was evident that most of the teachers in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were engaged in supporting students in identification of career needs. Literature (Stambulova and Wylleman (2019); Torregrosa et al., 2015) also revealed that shown that career education is an important starting point for gaining life skills with sports, especially in the beginning period. Therefore, career teachers, coaches, sports managers, mentors etc. who teach sports to children and young people should be encouraged to always engage the children for development of dual career. Further, it would be beneficial for them to consider the role of sport in providing life skills. Families who want their children to be prepared for the dual career in life in the best way should be aware that sports help to acquire and develop many life skills. Finally, it may be suggested that they encourage their children by directing them to sports and support them in this direction.

With regard to students' individual interests and identification of career needs, the participants had varied views. For instance, in a face-to-face interview with one of the directors of studies in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, he said:

"Unlike our school, most school do not have enough spare for dual career development that centre of interest is basically academic. Identification at the students individual abilities help in specialization of what they can do best when gained well they can be more active in class since they of in those who are also good in other helps it gives a learner a wide range of thinking."

From the quotation, it implied that the teachers consider the students' interest as a basis for supporting them in identification of career needs. However, the participants lamented that some parents tend to derail their children by making them shift their interest too early. For instance, one of the directors of studies (R-DOS-04) said;

"Parenting that tend to shift the learners career choices against the learners own interest. Some parents would wish that their children becomes what they want other than what they (learners) are interested in. The community where the learners come from may not be one which follows the learners and career development as in some communities may have a mid of only sport and not academics in addition the peers of the learners can also either affect the learners duel career development positively or negatively. The nature of the teachers as in some teachers may end up demotivating learners towards some careers depending on what they deem to necessary."

Further still, on the influence of identification of students' career needs one of the directors of studies (R-DHT-02) said;

"Identification of students' career needs had a effect positive since, the talent is identified earlier and enables learners to perfect their talents. By so doing they can achieve in a wide lunge of life aspects."

The implication was that if the students' career needs are not identified early, it becomes disadvantageous to the student. Indeed, another director of studies (R-DOS-05) said;

"If a student career needs are not detected early, he may end you taking a direction not suitable for their lives and talent in most cases such students study courses at university out of their the learners start perfecting the skills of their interest early. A case in point are students who are good at athletics. If they are identified early enough, they can be very good athletic. Ability to identity a student's career early enables the country to have right human resources of the right pretensions and offices. If a student is guided early and in a proper way then teachers become teachers and these good in medicine to medical."

The qualitative results on influence of identification of students' career needs corroborated closely with studies of other scholars such as Öztürk (2018) who discovered that although majority of students had sufficient sports facilities in their schools, it was observed that 68.1% of them participate in some sports activities offered in the schools. Another study whose results corroborated closely with the results of this study was the study carried by Özcan and Yıldırım (2011). According to their findings, the social skill levels of the secondary school students who engaged in licensed sports compared to those who engage in sports at their schools revealed a significant difference (Özcan et al, 2011). In other words, social skill levels affective sensitivity dimension differs significantly depending on the nature of sports the students engage in both in school and outside school. When one considers the difference between the state of sports, it is seen that there is a difference in favor of students doing licensed sports than those doing sporting activities in the schools. Students who engage in licensed sports gain more life skills than those who do not.

The results are further supported by Mayer (2017) who indicated that participation in sporting activities has great benefits. Mayer (2017) found out that secondary school students who participated in sporting activities gained more life skills such as time management, leadership, communication, teamwork, emotional skills, social skills and goal setting than those who did not participate in sporting activities. According to Mayer (2017), students who play in school teams gain more life skills such as time management, leadership, communication, teamwork, emotional skills, social skills and goal setting than those who do not play in school teams. Furthermore, students who engage in team sports are more likely to acquire life skills such as communication, time management, leadership, social skills, teamwork and goal setting, compared to those engaged in individual sports. It can be said that this is due to the fact that the students gain and develop many life skills as a result of social interaction with sports.

In discussing the results relating to identification of career needs, it is important to reflect on the whole purpose of career education. According to Gordon (2016) the purpose of career education is to help students identify, explore and make informed choices about the kind of careers they need to develop in their lifetime. In this regard, students need to be supported to identify their career needs in order to explore and plan for their future career endeavours based on their interests, skills and values. Provision of career education can be beneficial in many ways including; learning to successfully balance two or more aspects of life without sacrificing one's prime pursuits and reach his/her potential in both areas; opportunity to enhance current skills, develop one's life skills and become more well-rounded; chance to expand one's social networks beyond academics or sports; enhanced employment prospects with transferable skills for the future; and prevention of identity crisis which allows one to expand his/her identity.

Furthermore, identification of one's career needs is important because it helps the individual to know himself/herself in terms of his/her strengths, weaknesses, aptitude, perception, passion, interests and ambitions which should be taken into account while selecting a lifetime career. The finding of the study revealed that students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region were supported by career teachers to be able to identify career needs. In doing so, many students identified several academic careers such as aspiring to be doctors, lawyers, teachers, architects, engineers and so on. This implied that on the whole, the respondents agreed that there were many student aspiring to take on academic careers for their future life. It was also found out that identification of career needs was significantly related to development of academic careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. The findings were in agreement with earlier studies on career education and career development among studies. For instance, the findings were in agreement with Gordon (2016) who found out that advising students on career options and opportunities helped them to make decisions on which academic career to undertake for life.

Similarly, Leslie-Too-good & Gill (2018) found out that career education helps students to identify and make decisions with regard to various academic careers by enabling learners to make meaningful choices about their choice of study (career counseling and guidance); providing information on learning programmes, education and training providers, qualifications and job opportunities; and providing life skills for all students and facilitating access to counseling services, where required.

The findings of this study further indicated that for every unit effort in supporting students' identification of career needs in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, was accompanied by a 29.7% improvement in development of academic careers. This implies that there is a strong significant influence of supporting students in identification of career needs and development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. These findings were in agreement with various studies such as that those by Borggreffe and Cachay (2012); Stambulova et al., (2015 as well as the European Commission (2012) which identified the difficulty of combining an athletic and academic career simultaneously and being successful in both areas. Coping with tasks in these areas is known as a dual career. Experts are concerned that in a dual career academic success suffers from the challenges posed by the athletic career (Creutzburg and Scheid, 2014; Huml et al., 2019). Besides individual opportunity costs, expenses made for an athletic career might result in a less successful academic career (Emrich et al., 2009). The comprehensive review by Thompson et al. (2022) highlights that the research on academic success in a dual career is inconclusive. Although student-athletes at sport schools receive considerably more support in academia and athletics, student-athletes suffer from missing school and attaining higher education access (Thompson et al., 2022).

The findings of this study revealed that majority of the respondents agreed that there were students who liked to take up sports careers in future. This implied that identification of career needs was also significantly related to development of sports careers among students in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. For every unit effort in supporting students' identification of career needs in the secondary schools in Sebei sub-region, was accompanied by a 7.2% improvement in development of sports careers. This implied that there was also a strong significant influence of supporting students in identification of career needs and development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region.

Considering the magnitude of influence, identification of students' career needs had a much higher influence for academic than for sports career development. Influence on academic career development was more than four times (29.7% to 7.2%) higher than for sports career development. This means that out of every five (5) students supported to identify their career needs, four (4) would choose to engage in an academic career development while only one (1) would choose to engage in a sports career development. The findings corroborated with findings from studies that investigated elite athletes' career

pathways that indicated that they typically follow one of three trajectories: (a) focusing exclusively on sport; (b) combining sport and education/work while prioritizing sports-based development; and (c) constructing a stable dual career pathway. These three pathways, labeled as linear, convergent, and parallel (Torregrosa et al., 2015), are associated with different psycho-social implications of career transitions (e.g., career ending injury), with only the stable dual career trajectory being found to safeguard athletes' broader personal development, employability, and re-integration into society after careers in elite sport (Barriopedro et al., 2019; L'opez de Subijana et al., 2020).

5. CONCLUSIONS

Given the study findings and the discussion therefrom, the study concluded that there is a strong significant influence of supporting students in identification of career needs and development of academic careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. There is also a strong significant influence of supporting students in identification of career needs and development of sports careers among students in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region. However, by comparison, identification of students' career needs in secondary schools in Sebei sub-region had a higher magnitude of influence for academic than for sports career development. Given the same support towards identification of career needs, more students would opt to choose an academic career for development than a sports career.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. To be able to support students in identification of career needs, the teachers should be trained and empowered with the requisite information about the various careers available for students to choose from.
- ii. Career guidance should not be provided to a selected few but rather to all students so as to enable every students be able to make appropriate choices.
- iii. Career teachers should engage with personnel from different government and non-governmental organizations to be able to provide a wide scope of information about careers; thus, enable student's wide scope of choices to identify their own life careers.

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